

USING THE METHOD OF SIMULATING REALITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Today, the imitation method is used internationally in all fields of science, including philosophy, sociology, economics, pedagogy, psychology, art, etc. In the pedagogical direction, the imitation method is manifested in mutual backwardness with synergetics. This method, in turn, together with the method of synergetics, serves to eliminate negative approaches in education.*

Keywords: *effective methods, education, teaching, methodology*

A good teacher should have the ability to analyze and enrich the educational process. For this, the pedagogue is required to regularly reflect on the learning process and students' cognitive activities. The main goal is to achieve the desired result using the most effective methods. It is necessary for every teacher to analyze teaching methods based on internal conditions and external requirements, make corrections to them, and enrich them with a creative approach. Modern educational concepts are characterized by determination of the student's own position and orientation towards self-development. For this, students are required to be able to perform various forms of work individually and collectively with teachers. Such work methods include holding small conferences, working in problem groups, participating in trainings together, defending projects, participating in seminars, debates, and simulation games. Teachers try to activate students using different methods within the framework of their professional knowledge and outlook.

The term innovation is used in school pedagogy in several senses. In the process of applying the concept of innovation, pedagogues attach the meaning of alternative to it. With the help of innovations, qualitatively new educational results, new forms of teaching, abandonment of existing methods are understood. At the present time, when the process of reforming school education is being implemented, the scope of efforts to implement the method of information-based approach to the educational process is expanding. On the basis of this approach, a rich stock of knowledge related to the educational subject is presented to the students. Among such knowledge, it is possible to include specially processed information within the academic discipline. In addition, taking into account the uniqueness of each person, educational materials suitable for his abilities, his position, self-awareness, realization of his personal development, identity, thinking, understanding, goal-setting it is required to apply methods that allow the development of competences in the field of acquisition, reflection, interdisciplinary skills.

In recent years, education has been required to harmonize the student with certain ways of thinking and to implement educational activities, and to take into account the individual characteristics of students' interests in this process. Such a process is carried out on the basis of communication between the teacher and the students. In this process, teachers mediate between existing cultural assets, values, goals, tools, ways of thinking and working. At the same time, they strive to present students with the image of themselves and the world around them, as well as cultural traditions. The knowledge presented in this process becomes the developing mass of students' minds, serves as a necessary tool for achieving the expected result and obtaining the

product of activity. In this process, the term innovation means replacing traditions to a certain extent. Such changes are carried out with the help of educational process management and methods. Scientific research is also important here. In addition, the term innovation has another meaning. It is related to traditions that do not change, but are enriched in terms of content. New ideas are created in order to raise the quality of the educational process to a higher level.

Innovation is reflected in many efforts to reform school education. This is being done directly by cultural, spiritual and economic changes in the society. Innovations ensure the emergence of new methods and didactic forms in pedagogical practice. The authors of such innovations are representatives of the scientific and pedagogical community. Innovative projects, methods within the framework of school education embody new perspectives, ideas, values, goals for the educational process, its existing aspects, development mechanisms, methods of student socialization, and are the main innovative activities of the teacher. determines the directions.

The implementation of the teacher's innovative activity is of great importance in raising the educational process to a new level of quality. As a result of the application of innovative methods, the formation and development of the student in the educational process accelerates. A legitimate question arises as to who are the subjects of the innovation process. Subjects of the innovative pedagogical process are primarily teachers and students. It can be seen that the effectiveness of pedagogical activity of an innovative nature is the product of the joint activity of the subjects of the process. Their efforts will achieve the guaranteed result. In order to ensure the effectiveness of innovative methods and methods, it requires a wide use of the intellectual capabilities of students and pedagogical resources. Innovative methods and techniques are always created to replace outdated ones, and are supposed to give the opportunity to achieve greater efficiency than them. In order to ensure pedagogical efficiency, it is required to use resources that are compatible with innovative methods and methods.

To date, there is a lack of resources necessary for the educational process. Sufficient educational resources are required to ensure the effectiveness of innovative methods and methods. In addition, teachers should be able to overcome stagnation in their minds. Any innovative methods and methods can be mechanisms of intellectual development of students. With the help of this mechanism, students' perception, thinking activity, concepts, intuition, and learning activities have been developed. Innovative methods serve to ensure the personal development of students. At the same time, it creates confidence in the teacher and the student. In this process, the teacher tries to carry out a full-fledged professional activity. Pedagogical activities carried out in school education are considered in this process. The student will be able to deepen his knowledge, socialize, learn the legal and normative foundations, learn the rules, adapt to the conditions. One such innovative method is innovation.

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The imitation method is first of all directly related to the concept of activity. Activities include ideas, concepts, goals, values, tasks, knowledge, tools, methods, processes, abilities, all concepts related to pedagogical activity. In addition, the activity is manifested in direct connection with imitation, including setting goals, forming new ideas, analyzing results, reflection, conducting small research. Some parts of the activity may not be involved in this process. The question arises as to which of its components must be involved in order for the activity to take place. This is related to the individual characteristics of the student. If the student does not achieve the final results of his activity, his activity efficiency will be low. The results achieved by students are determined and evaluated in the pedagogical process through specific criteria. If students are given specific goals, they will achieve the desired results. In this case, the imitation method has special possibilities.

Today, the imitation method is used in the educational systems of many developed countries. The method of imitation means the exchange of places with the concrete activity of a person. In the encyclopedia of pedagogy, the imitation method is defined as follows. Imitation (lat. imitatio - imitation) - 1) imitation of something, simile [1, p. 76].

Social phenomena in society are understood within the concept of imitation. Imitation contains motifs of repetition. Processes and actions are repeated within the concept of imitation. Imitation is manifested in all spheres of social life. Its basis is simulation to natural reality, repetition is manifested in its composition. Imitation is an activity-based, intended method of movement. Imitation is used as a research method in various disciplines. The functions of various systems and socio-economic objects are clearly displayed in it. Especially with the help of a computer, the progress of the process and the parameters representing it are reflected using the simulation method. Game technology is the basis of imitation. In this case, processes similar to this or that event are created. Such events happen in real life. In the process of education, similar situations are created. By simulating various events, a favorable pedagogical situation is created for conveying to students. The well-known American psychologist J. G. Mead commented on the development of the process of self-awareness and noted that the process of personality formation consists of three stages. Its first stage is imitation. At this stage, students imitate the behavior of adults and copy their actions. The second stage is the game stage. In this process, they understand that behavioral actions consist of fulfilling different roles. As a result of the transition from one role to another, students present to each other the views, thoughts, ideas presented to them by the members of society. In this way, students will be able to learn historical and social experience. According to Mead, the third stage is the stage of participation in team games. In this process, students will be able to understand the nature of their actions and those of their peers. If the teacher uses historical stereotypes in the form of a micro-experiment every day in each lesson, it becomes a methodical experience for both the student and the teacher and develops the professional skills of the teacher [2, p. 11].

The famous pedagogue P.F.Lesgaft created the theory of action games and divided them into two groups: imitation games for students, games for students. In contrast to game-based, goal-oriented simulation games have the character of encouraging students to be creative. He embodies the objective reality before the eyes of the reader and encourages them to think creatively. The images of historical figures and their activities based on creativity create a stimulus for students'

creative thinking. Actions performed in the process of simulation games have their own clear limits and are directed to achieve specific conditions, directions, rules and educational goals.

When using simulation games in the educational process, its construction is unique and provides convenient opportunities for student development. The method of imitation modeling has been used since the 60s and 70s of the 20th century. Imitation, imitative modeling is a method of representing the main aspects of reality. It is a pedagogical phenomenon consisting of simulated situations based on deep and detailed research based on the analysis of specific situations. Imitation is carried out in order to understand the general or specific aspects of reality. Organization of the educational process in the process of simulation modeling is of particular importance in instilling historical knowledge and historical thinking in history classes. Imitation methods are used to develop students in the process of studying specific situations. In such situations, the student is the main subject of the process. The simulation modeling method was fully developed at Harvard in the 80s of the last century. Initially, the imitation method was used in business schools. After that, it was widely applied to the process of professional education and used in the training of management specialists. To date, the imitation method is widely used in pedagogical processes as well as in many other fields.

In recent years, specific efforts have been made in the field of introducing didactic developments in order to study specific situations in the educational process. Simulation modeling can be included among such methods. This can be seen in the following. The basis of simulation modeling is the study of concrete situations. The participants of the process are involved in the discussion of specific life situations. In this case, students work on real life evidence, not some invented one

In the process of using the imitation method, the group of students occupies a special place. Because the ideas that arise during the discussion and the proposed solutions are the product of the students' joint activities. There are several options for studying specific situations using the simulation method. In all of them, students are given a certain amount of time to work on the evidence being studied. It is also possible to use several alternative options for presenting educational materials to students using the imitation method. They are: traditional extended forms, reduced form, multimedia tools, documentaries. Life events are reflected in such digital media.

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